

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Isolation and Characterization of Antagonistic Bacteria from the Gut of *Lampito mauritii* (Kinberg, 1866)

OPEN ACCESS**Received:** 09-11-2023**Accepted:** 16-12-2023**Published:** 12-01-2024

Citation: Balagangatharan P, Ramkumar R, Raja P (2024) Isolation and Characterization of Antagonistic Bacteria from the Gut of *Lampito mauritii* (Kinberg, 1866). Indian Journal of Science and Technology 17(2): 194-203. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17i2.2765>

* **Corresponding author.**

psbgangatharan@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2024 Balagangatharan et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](#))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

P Balagangatharan^{1*}, R Ramkumar², P Raja³

1 Research scholar (Regd. No. 21211282191006), Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous-Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627012, Tamil Nadu), Palayamkottai, 627002, Tamil Nadu, India

2 Research scholar (Regd. No. 18211282011024), Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous-Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627012, Tamil Nadu), Palayamkottai, 627002, Tamil Nadu, India

3 Assistant professor, Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous-Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627012, Tamil Nadu), Palayamkottai, 627002, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

Objective: To isolate and characterize potentially antagonistic bacteria from the gut of *Lampito mauritii* earthworms. **Methods:** *Lampito mauritii* earthworms were collected and gut bacteria were isolated on nutrient agar. Antibacterial activity of isolates was checked by well diffusion against fish and human pathogens. Potent isolates were characterized biochemically. Antimicrobial metabolites were extracted from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolate TR07 using ethyl acetate and tested by disc diffusion. TR07 was identified by 16S rRNA gene sequencing and phylogenetic analysis. Antibacterial efficacy was assessed statistically. **Results:** Among 38 discrete isolates, 4 exhibited antibacterial activity against *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Staphylococcus aureus* in well-diffusion assay. These 4 isolates were characterized as *Pseudomonas* sp., *Vibrio* sp., *Aeromonas* sp., and *Bacillus* sp. based on biochemical tests. Antimicrobial metabolites extracted from *Pseudomonas* sp. TR07 using ethyl acetate showed statistically significant inhibition against gram-positive and gram-negative bacterial fish and human pathogens in disc diffusion assay. The 16S rRNA gene sequencing and phylogenetic analysis identified the potent isolate TR07 as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with 99.62% sequence homology. **Novelty:** In a fortuitous finding, the antibacterial potency of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was dramatically amplified through the utilization of a strikingly minute concentration of the bacterial culture extract.

Keywords: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; Earthworm gut; Antibacterial metabolites; Human pathogens; Fish pathogens

1 Introduction

Earthworms belonging to the annelid phylum inhabit and enrich soil ecosystems across tropical and temperate regions⁽¹⁾. As ecosystem engineers, earthworms facilitate decomposition, nutrient mineralization, soil aeration, and water filtration through burrowing and feeding activities⁽²⁾. Culture-independent metagenomic analysis has revealed functional diversity within the gut microbiome linked to carbohydrate metabolism, defenses against pathogens, and antagonism^(3–5).

The anecic earthworm *Lampito mauritii* is widely distributed across the Indo-Malayan region⁽⁶⁾. Metagenomic characterization of *L. mauritii* gut contents has uncovered a rich repository of antimicrobial resistance genes and biosynthetic gene clusters^(7,8). Rapid expansion of the aquaculture industry has been plagued by frequent outbreaks of infectious diseases resulting in substantial economic losses^(9,10). A bacterial infection caused by *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Aeromonas veronii* and *Aeromonas caviae* that is common in freshwater fish. It can cause bloody spots or ulcers, ragged fins, or enlarged eyes, fluid accumulation in the abdomen. These issues underscore the need for the prospection of novel antimicrobials from relatively unexplored natural sources like the gut microbiome.

This research aimed to isolate and characterize antimicrobial-producing gut bacteria from the *Lampito mauritii* to identify novel leads for therapeutic applications. The pressing need for sustainable alternatives to antibiotics in aquaculture, driven by economic losses and the rise of antibiotic resistance in infectious diseases, underscored the importance of this exploration. The study aimed to contribute to the development of sustainable therapies by thoroughly examining and understanding the antimicrobial properties inherent in the gut symbionts of *L. mauritii*, potentially offering viable solutions for both aquaculture and broader public health concerns.

2 Methodology

Fig 1. Graphical representation of isolation and characterization of earthworm gut bacteria

2.1 Sample Collection and Earthworm Identification

The *Lampito mauritii* was obtained in sufficient numbers from the Tamirabarani river bank (8°45'39.2" N 77°44'38.4" E) in the Tirunelveli District of Tamil Nadu, India. Samples were collected manually by shoveling and hand sorting the topsoil at a depth of 20 cm⁽¹¹⁾. The specimens were taxonomically identified to species level by examining the diagnostic morphological characters such as body pigmentation, the position of the clitellum, the number of segments, and the arrangement of setae using standard taxonomic keys⁽¹²⁾.

2.2 Isolation of Gut Bacteria

Five freshly collected earthworms were surface sterilized using 70% ethanol and rinsed in sterile phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). The gut was dissected out aseptically and homogenized in PBS under laminar flow conditions by vigorous vortexing with silica bead. The homogenate was serially diluted up to 10⁻⁷ dilutions and 100 µl of each dilution was spread plated on sterile Nutrient agar (Himedia) plates. The plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 48 hours. Discrete bacterial colonies exhibiting distinct morphology were picked and purified by quadruplicate streaking. The axenic cultures obtained were preserved as glycerol stocks at 4 °C for further studies⁽¹³⁾. Isolated strains were given designated codes

2.3 Preliminary Antibacterial screening

To conduct an initial assessment of the antimicrobial capabilities of bacteria isolated from the gut, a colony overlay method, as detailed by⁽¹⁴⁾ was employed. Both the indicator strains and the isolated bacteria were cultured in Nutrient broth (Himedia-M002) and incubated overnight at 27°C. 100 µl of the indicator strain culture at a concentration of 10⁵ CFU/ml was evenly spread on Muller Hinton Agar (MHA) plates using a sterile cotton-tipped swab. Following the drying of the culture, drops of the isolated bacterial cultures were carefully dispensed onto the agar plates. After a 24-hour incubation period at 28°C, the assessment of antimicrobial activity was conducted by examining the presence of zones of inhibition surrounding the bacterial colonies. The scoring system outlined by⁽¹⁵⁾ was used, and based on the cumulative scores obtained, the most promising antagonistic bacteria against the indicator strains were selected for further investigation.

2.4 Phenotypic and Biochemical Characterization

The colony morphology of the selected isolates was documented. Gram-staining was performed and observed under a light microscope at 100X magnification. Biochemical tests such as indole production, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, citrate utilization, catalase, oxidase, nitrate reduction, glucose fermentation, motility, and hydrogen sulfide production were performed as described in Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology⁽¹⁶⁾.

2.5 Extraction of Antibacterial Metabolites

The selected antagonistic bacterial isolate (TR07) was grown in Nutrient broth at 37°C for 72 hours to stimulate maximal secondary metabolite production. The culture broth was centrifuged at 10,000 g for 15 minutes and the cell-free supernatant was extracted twice using ethyl acetate at a 1:1 ratio. The organic phase containing the extracted antibacterial metabolites was concentrated by vacuum evaporation and makeup the solution as 25mg/ml of ethyl acetate for antimicrobial assay.

2.6 Antibacterial assay

The disc diffusion method was employed to determine the antibacterial efficacy of the extracted metabolites⁽¹⁷⁾. Sterile paper discs were impregnated with 100 µl of the extract solution and after complete evaporation of the solvent, placed on Mueller-Hinton agar plates and swabbed uniformly with the 12 h culture of Fish pathogens viz., *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Vibrio* sp., and Human pathogens viz., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Bacillus cereus*. A standard antibiotic (Streptomycin-10 mcg) was used as the positive control. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and the zone of inhibition was measured. The relative percentage inhibitions (PIs) for the ethyl acetate extract with respect to Streptomycin-10 mcg were calculated by using the following formula according to⁽¹⁸⁾.

$$\% \text{ of Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Ethyl acetate extract} - \text{Negative control}}{\text{Positive control} - \text{Negative control}}$$

Experiments were conducted in triplicate, and results are presented as mean ± standard deviation. Statistical analysis employed SPSS v.22 software, involving one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test, to discern significant differences among test

samples ($P \leq 0.05$).

2.7 Molecular Identification and Phylogenetic Analysis

Genomic DNA was extracted from the most potent bacterial isolate (TR07) using a commercial kit (Qiagen D Neasy Blood & Tissue kit). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was performed using the universal 16S rRNA gene primers 27F (5' AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3') and 1492R (5'TACGGYTACCTTGTTACG ACTT-3')⁽¹⁹⁾ the amplified PCR product was sequenced bidirectionally using an automated sequencer (Applied Biosystems 3500XL). The 16S rRNA gene sequence obtained was analyzed for the closest sequence match by NCBI BLAST analysis. A phylogenetic tree was constructed using the Neighbor-Joining algorithm in MEGAX software⁽²⁰⁾.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Isolation and Preliminary Screening of Earthworm Gut Bacteria

A total of 38 phenotypically diverse bacterial isolates were recovered aseptically from the dissected gut of *Lampito mauritii* on Nutrient agar following aerobic incubation for 48 hours. Out of these 38 isolates, 4 isolates named TR07, TR12, TR22, and TR23 exhibited remarkably potent antibacterial activities based on appreciably large zones of inhibition against the indicator strains *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. These 4 isolates were selected for further morphological and biochemical-based identification. (Table 1, Figure 2)

Table 1. Preliminary Antibacterial screening

Isolates	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>
TR01	++	+++
TR02	-	-
TR03	-	-
TR04	++	+++
TR05	+	-
TR06	-	-
TR07	++	++++
TR08	++	-
TR09	+	+
TR10	-	-
TR11	++	-
TR12	++	++++
TR13	++	-
TR14	+++	+++
TR15	-	-
TR16	+++	-
TR17	++	-
TR18	-	-
TR19	-	-
TR20	++	-
TR21	-	-
TR22	++	++++
TR23	++	+++
TR24	-	-
TR25	+	+
TR26	-	-
TR27	++	-
TR28	-	-
TR29	+	++
TR30	++	-
TR31	-	-
TR32	-	++
TR33	++	+

Continued on next page

Table 1 continued

TR34	-	-
TR35	-	+
TR36	-	-
TR37	+	+
TR38	+	-

+= <1mm; ++ = 1 to 3mm; +++ = >3mm; (+, ++, +++ indicates zone of inhibition in range); - = No activity

Fig 2. Screening for Anti-bacterial activity

3.2 Phenotypic and Biochemical Profiling

Gram staining performed on fresh cultures showed that isolates TR07 and TR22 were gram-negative bacilli, whereas isolates TR12 and TR23 were gram-positive bacilli. Biochemical tests such as indole production, Voges-Proskauer methyl red, citrate utilization, oxidase, catalase, nitrate reduction, glucose fermentation, motility, and hydrogen sulfide production could characterize isolates TR07, TR12, TR22 and TR23 presumptively as species of *Pseudomonas*, *Vibrio*, *Aeromonas* and *Bacillus* respectively based on the observations matched with standard biochemical profiles. (Table 2, Figure 3)

Table 2. Phenotypic and Biochemical Profiling of Selected Isolates

Isolates	TR07	TR12	TR22	TR23
	Morphology			
Gram Stain	-	+	-	+
Motility	+	+	-	+
Pigment	Green	White	Green	White
Shape	Rod	Rod	Rod	Rod

Continued on next page

Table 2 continued				
Bio-Chemical Test				
Indole	+	-	-	-
Methyl red	-	-	-	+
Voges Poskauer	-	-	-	-
Citrate	+	-	+	+
Oxidase	+	+	+	-
Catalase	+	+	+	+
H ₂ S Production	-	+	-	+
Starch	-	+	-	-
Nitrate Reduction Test	-	-	+	+
Gelatinase	+	-	+	-
Sugar Utilization				
Sucrose	+	+	+	-
Glucose	+	+	+	-
Rhamnose	-	-	-	-
Maltose	+	-	+	-
Lactose	-	+	+	-
Mannitol	+	+	+	-
Identified organisms	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>Vibrio</i>	<i>Aeromonas</i>	<i>Bacillus</i>

+ = Presence/Positive result, - = Absence/Negative results

3.3 Anti-bacterial assay

The ethyl acetate extract of isolate TR07 showed statistically significant broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against all indicator strains tested, including Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus* and Gram-negative bacteria *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio* sp. and *Aeromonas hydrophila* ($p > 0.001$ for all strains), with the percent inhibition ranging from 67.55% to 97.87%. The highest mean inhibitions of 24.00 ± 0.25 mm and 23.33 ± 0.39 mm were seen against *B. cereus* and *S. aureus* respectively, while the lowest mean inhibition of 17.16 ± 0.39 mm was seen against *S. typhi* (Figures 4 and 5). Positive controls showed significantly greater inhibition than negative controls for all strains ($p = .001$ or $.005$), indicating the ethyl acetate extract has strong antimicrobial potential, especially against *B. cereus* and *S. aureus*. (Table 3)

Table 3. Antibacterial activity

Indicator strains	Samples	Mean \pm S.E	F ; p	Percentage of inhibition
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	S	14.83 \pm 0.37	$F_{2,1} = 385.24; p = .001$	72.88
	P	20.16 \pm 0.68		
	N	00.50 \pm 0.26		
<i>Vibrio</i> sp.	S	18.50 \pm 0.24	$F_{2,1} = 1099.357; p = .005$	80.75
	P	22.83 \pm 0.40		
	N	0.333 \pm 0.30		
<i>Salmonella Typhi</i>	S	17.16 \pm 0.39	$F_{2,1} = 1006.118; p = .005$	67.55
	P	25.16 \pm 0.41		
	N	00.50 \pm 0.25		
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	S	23.33 \pm 0.39	$F_{2,1} = 1146.600; p = .001$	97.87
	P	23.83 \pm 0.40		
	N	0.333 \pm 0.14		
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	S	24.00 \pm 0.25	$F_{2,1} = 2402.375; p = .005$	96.61
	P	24.83 \pm 0.15		
	N	0.333 \pm 0.30		

S- Ethyl acetate extract of isolate TR07; P- Positive Control; N- Negative control; S.E – Standard Error, F- Frequency, p – significance

Fig 3. Biochemical characterization

Fig 4. Antibacterial activity of Ethyl acetate extract of the Isolate TR07

Fig 5. Anti-bacterial activity of Ethyl acetate extract of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Strain CAREB01 [TR07 – Ethyl acetate extract isolate TR07 (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Strain CAREB01); P – Positive control; N-Negative control]

3.4 Molecular Identification and Phylogenetic Analysis

Comparison of the nearly complete 16S rRNA gene sequence (~1450 bp) by BLAST analysis revealed 99.62% sequence similarity and closest homology of TR07 to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains. The construction of a Neighbor-Joining phylogenetic tree with reference sequences also indicated clear taxonomic clustering and grouping of the isolate TR07 within the *P. aeruginosa* clade (Figure 6). Both molecular approaches firmly confirmed the identity of isolate TR07 as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The sequence has been submitted in NCBI GenBank with accession number OQ804675.1 as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain CAREB01.

4 Discussion

Earthworms drive a vital ecological role in soils through burrowing, feeding, and casting activities. These behaviors enhance organic matter decomposition, nutrient cycling, aeration, and water infiltration. Earthworm activities improve soil fertility, porosity, and tilth, leading to increased ecosystem productivity and sustainability⁽²⁾. The gut microbes promote growth, sexual maturation, pathogen inhibition, and overall fitness in their hosts through these metabolic activities⁽¹⁾. Culture-independent metagenomic analysis has revealed that the microbiota associated in gut is dominated by anaerobic fermentative bacteria from phyla such as Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Bacteroidetes⁽²¹⁾. In this study, 38 culturable bacterial isolates were recovered, active isolates were identified as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Vibrio*, *Aeromonas*, and *Bacillus* sp.,

Most active *P. aeruginosa* is a ubiquitous gram-negative proteobacterium and reported elsewhere to secrete a range of bioactive secondary metabolites such as phenazines, quinolones, rhamnolipids, lectins, hydrogen cyanide, siderophores, proteases, and other extracellular enzymes with roles in toxicity, virulence, nutrient acquisition, competition, and defense^(21,22). The liquid-liquid extraction using ethyl acetate could recover broad-spectrum antimicrobial metabolites from *P. aeruginosa* TR07. Previous study had done on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* had revealed the ability of inhabitation against bacterial pathogens with average zone of inhibition as 16.64 mm while the average zone of inhibition of this current study was 19.56 mm was relatively high with 2.5mg on compare to the 10mg per disc⁽²³⁾. The extract displayed appreciable antibacterial efficacy against *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-positive pathogens as well as gram-negative bacteria *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio*

Fig 6. Evolutionary relationship of taxa by a neighbor-joining method

sp, and *Aeromonas hydrophila*. This reveals the antimicrobial potential of earthworm gut microbes, which can be further translated into pharmacological applications. The observed activity is substantiated by Liquid-liquid extraction using ethyl acetate to recover broad-spectrum antimicrobials from *L. mauritii* gut bacteria. Other studies have reported anti-viral, anti-fungal, insecticidal, and probiotic activities of bacteria inhabiting the earthworm intestine^(24–26). Their diverse antimicrobial compounds provide a cheaper and safer alternative to conventional antibiotics used in biomedicine, veterinary practice, and aquaculture⁽²⁷⁾. For instance, Phenazine-1-carboxamide from a gut *Pseudomonas* strain exhibited broad-spectrum inhibition against fish pathogens like *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Edwardsiella tarda*, and *Streptococcus liniae*⁽²⁸⁾. Such examples underscore the merits of exploring this unique intestinal ecosystem through integrated microbiological, metagenomic, metabolomic, and chemical ecology approaches.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates the antibacterial potential of earthworm gut symbionts against fish and human pathogens. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* TR07 recovered from the *Lampito mauritii* exhibited broad-spectrum antagonism mediated by antibacterial metabolites extractable through ethyl acetate. Further purification and characterization of these bioactive compounds can reveal drug leads for treating infectious fish and human diseases. This provides the impetus for further explorations of earthworm gut microbial diversity as a treasure trove of therapeutic phytochemicals and antimicrobials.

References

- 1) Blouin M, Hodson ME, Delgado EA, Baker G, Brussaard L, Butt KR, et al. A review of earthworm impact on soil function and ecosystem services. *European Journal of Soil Science*. 2013;64(2):161–182. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12025>.
- 2) Kumar R, Yadav R, Gupta RK, Yodha K, Kataria SK, Kadyan P, et al. The Earthworms: Charles Darwin's Ecosystem Engineer. In: Hakeem KR, Grichar WJ, editors. *Organic Fertilizers - New Advances and Applications*. Agricultural Sciences;IntechOpen. 2023. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/1131574>.
- 3) Wüst PK, Horn MA, Drake HL. Clostridiaceae and Enterobacteriaceae as active fermenters in earthworm gut content. *The ISME Journal*. 2011;5(1):92–106. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2010.99>.

- 4) Hu L, Robert CAM, Cadot S, Zhang XI, Ye M, Li B, et al. Root exudate metabolites drive plant-soil feedbacks on growth and defense by shaping the rhizosphere microbiota. *Nature Communications*. 2018;9(1):1–13. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05122-7>.
- 5) Kim Y, Koh I, Rho M. Deciphering the human microbiome using next-generation sequencing data and bioinformatics approaches. *Methods*. 2015;79:80:52–59. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jymeth.2014.10.022>.
- 6) Priya S, Santhi S. Effect of vermicomposts on the growth of amaranthus plants and soil fertility. *Advances in Applied Science Research*. 2014;5(1):231–240. Available from: <https://www.primescholars.com/articles/effect-of-vermicomposts-on-the-growth-of-amaranthus-plants-and-soil-fertility.pdf>.
- 7) Thakur SS, Lone AR, Tiwari N, Jain SK, Yadav S. Metagenomic Exploration of Bacterial Community Structure of Earthworms' Gut. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*. 2021;15(3):1156–1172. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.22207/jpam15305>.
- 8) Walke JB, Becker MH, Loftus SC, House LL, Cormier G, Jensen RV, et al. Amphibian skin may select for rare environmental microbes. *The ISME Journal*. 2014;8(11):2207–2217. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2014.77>.
- 9) Subasinghe RP, Bondad-Reantaso MG, McGladdery SE. Aquaculture development, health and wealth. 2001. Available from: <https://library.enaca.org/General/pag167-197.htm>.
- 10) Bondad-Reantaso MG, Subasinghe RP, Arthur JR, Ogawa K, Chinabut S, Adlard R, et al. Disease and health management in Asian aquaculture. *Veterinary Parasitology*. 2005;132(3-4):249–272. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2005.07.005>.
- 11) Blakemore RJ. Japanese earthworms (Annelida: Oligochaeta): a review and checklist of species. *Organisms Diversity & Evolution*. 2003;3(3):241–244. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1078/1439-6092-00082>.
- 12) Sambrook J, Fritsch EF, Maniatis T. Molecular cloning: a laboratory manual. 2nd ed. Cold spring harbor laboratory press. 1989. Available from: <https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.474251/page/n1/mode/2up>.
- 13) Bauer AW, Kirby WMM, Sherris JC, Turck M. Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing by a Standardized Single Disk Method. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology*. 1966;45(4):493–496. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5325707/>.
- 14) Alonso S, Castro MC, Berdasco M, de la Banda IG, Moreno-Ventas XG, de Rojas AH. Isolation and Partial Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria from the Gut Microbiota of Marine Fishes for Potential Application as Probiotics in Aquaculture. *Probiotics and Antimicrobial Proteins*. 2019;11(2):569–579. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12602-018-9439-2>.
- 15) Midhun SJ, Neethu S, Vysakh A, Sunil MA, Radhakrishnan EK, Jyothis M. Antibacterial activity of autochthonous bacteria isolated from *Anabas testudineus* (Bloch, 1792) and its in vitro probiotic characterization. *Microbial Pathogenesis*. 2017;113:312–320. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2017.10.058>.
- 16) Murray RGE, Holt JG. The History of Bergey's Manual. In: *Bergey's Manual of Systematics of Archaea and Bacteria*. 2015;p. 1–14. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118960608.BM00009>.
- 17) Ryan K, Ray C, Sherris J. Reviews and Notes: Infectious Diseases: Sherris Medical Microbiology: An Introduction to Infectious Diseases. *Annals of Internal Medicine*. 1995;122(11):888–888. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-122-11-199506010-00044>.
- 18) Kumar A, Shukla R, Singh P, Dubey NK. Chemical composition, antifungal and antiaflatoxic activities of *Ocimum sanctum* L. essential oil and its safety assessment as plant based antimicrobial. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*. 2010;48(2):539–543. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2009.11.028>.
- 19) Weisburg WG, Barns SM, Pelletier DA, Lane DJ. 16S ribosomal DNA amplification for phylogenetic study. *Journal of Bacteriology*. 1991;173(2):697–703. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1128/jb.173.2.697-703.1991>.
- 20) Kumar S, Stecher G, Li M, Knyaz C, Tamura K. MEGA X: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis across Computing Platforms. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 2018;35(6):1547–1549. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msy096>.
- 21) Breidenstein EBM, de la Fuente-Núñez C, Hancock REW. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: all roads lead to resistance. *Trends in Microbiology*. 2011;19(8):419–426. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2011.04.005>.
- 22) Moradali MF, Ghods S, Rehm BHA. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Lifestyle: A Paradigm for Adaptation, Survival, and Persistence. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*. 2017;7:1–29. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2017.00039>.
- 23) Amankwah FKD, Gbedema SY, Boakye YD, Bayor MT, Boamah VE. Antimicrobial Potential of Extract from a *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolate. *Scientifica*. 2022;2022:1–11. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4230397>.
- 24) Sruthy PB, Anjana JC, Rathinamala J, Jayashree S. The role of red pigment prodigiosin from bacteria of earthworm gut as an anticancer agent. *Journal of Microbiology Biotechnology and Food Sciences*. 2014;4(3):246–251. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.15414/jmbfs.2014-15.4.3.246-251>.
- 25) Parthasarathi K, Ranganathan LS, Anandi V, Zeyer J. Diversity of microflora in the gut and casts of tropical composting earthworms reared on different substrates. *Journal of Environmental Biology*. 2007;28(1):87–97. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17717992/>.
- 26) Mapile MRF, Obusan MCM. Mineralization, Biodegradation, and Antagonistic Activities of Gut-associated Bacteria and Fungi of African Nightcrawler, *Eudrilus eugeniae* (Kinberg, 1867). *Science Diliman*. 2020;32(1):42–67. Available from: <https://journals.upd.edu.ph/index.php/sciencediliman/article/view/7215>.
- 27) Hussain M, Liaqat I, Hanif U, Sultan A, Ara C, Aftab N, et al. Medicinal Perspective of Antibacterial Bioactive Agents in Earthworms (Clitellata, Annelida): A Comprehensive Review. *Journal of Oleo Science*. 2022;71(4):563–573. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5650/jos.ess21379>.
- 28) Citarasu T. Natural antimicrobial compounds for use in aquaculture. *Infectious Disease in Aquaculture*. 2012;p. 419–456. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857095732.3.419>.